

Kaniadakis Distribution and $e/T \ll 1$ Considerations Part 3

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In both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis $\exp_q(-e_i/T)$ and $\exp_k(-e_i/T)$ cases, the variable $-e_i/T$ is multiplied by either $(1-q)$ or k because in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ approximation, one obtains a polynomial representation of $\exp(-(1-q)e_i/T)$ or $\exp(-ke_i/T)$ to the power $1/(1-q)$ or $1/k$. Thus, we argue that e_i/T considerations are important. In Part I, we noted that in the Kaniadakis case for $e_i/T \ll 1$, one may consider that a full solution should collapse to $\exp(-ke_i/T) \approx 1 - ke_i/T + .5 (ke_i/T)(ke_i/T) + ((1)) \dots$. We noted that the Tsallis case only considers the first order term $-ke_i/T$ and so the Kaniadakis may be looked on as including the second order.

Here, we propose a more direct approach to obtaining the Kaniadakis distribution $\exp_k(-e_i/T)$ directly from ((1)) because ((1)) may be directly written as: $\exp(-ke_i/T) \approx -ke_i/T + \sqrt{(1 + (kke_i e_i)/(TT))}$. Furthermore, writing the solution in this form directly shows that it is the solution of a quadratic equation: $.5/B - .5/B = -ke_i/T$ which guarantees that $\exp_k(-e_i/T)\exp_k(e_i/T) = 1$, as noted in Part 2.

One may ask: Can one include a third order term in the expansion of ((1)). We show that one can and still maintain a quadratic form, but one no longer has the property $p(e)p(-e)=1$, although $k=0$ still yields Shannon results, which is a given because the $kkk e_i/Te_i/Te_i/T$, like the $kke_i e_i/(TT)$ drops out in the $k=0$ limit. Whether or not there is any physical relevance to the $kkke_i e_i/(TTT)$ result is not clear.

Low e_i/T Limit

Both the Tsallis $\exp_q(-e_i/T)$ and Kaniadakis $\exp_k(-e_i/T)$ represent polynomials taken to a power, namely $1/(1-q)$ and $1/k$. In the $1-q=0$ or $k=0$ limits, one should obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann $\exp(-e_i/T)$. The simplest polynomial which allows for this is to have $1 - (1-q) e_i/T$ or $1 - ke_i/T$ in the $1-q=0$ or $k=0$ limit which automatically becomes $\exp(-(1-q)e_i/T)$ or $\exp(-ke_i/T)$ such that $(1-q)$ and k cancel with the power. Even though one has a linear polynomial to a power in the $(1-q)=0$ and $k=0$ limits does not mean that the base function taken to a power is represented by this simple polynomial when the 0 limit does not hold. In the Tsallis case it does, but not in the Kaniadakis. In the latter case, however, the $k=0$ limit yields the polynomial form of $\exp(-ke_i/T)$ to second order.

We have noted in Parts I and 2 that given that $(1-q)$ and k are multiplied by $-e_i/T$ in the base function, one may just as well consider the limit $e_i/T \ll 1$.

Direct Kaniadakis From e_i/T Expansion of $\exp(-ke_i/T)$

In Part I, we derived the Kaniadakis base function in a somewhat convoluted manner by arguing that it must be equivalent to a second order in $-e_i/T$ expansion of $\exp(-ke_i/T)$. Here we obtain the same result directly because:

$$\exp(-ke_i/T) \approx 1 - ke_i/T + .5 (ke_i/T)((ke_i/T)) \approx -ke_i/T + \sqrt{(1 + kke_i e_i/(TT))} \quad ((2))$$

The second form in ((2)) is the Kaniadakis base function which is then taken to the power of $1/k$. Furthermore, one may see immediately that it is the solution of a quadratic equation:

$$.5p(e)p(e)^{-.5} + p(e) kei/T = 0 \quad ((3)) \quad \text{This may be written as:}$$

$$.5p(ei) - 5/p(e) = -kei/T \quad ((4))$$

$$((4)) \text{ leads immediately to the Kaniadakis: } \ln k(p) = \{ p(e)^k - p(e)^{-k} \} / (2k) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Also, one is guaranteed, through this quadratic, that } p(e)p(-e) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

Cubic Expansion

Given that the $\exp k(-ei/T)$ result follows directly from an $ei/T \ll 1$ quadratic expansion of $\exp(-kei/T)$, it seems reasonable to consider a cubic expansion:

$$\exp(-kei/T) \text{ approx} = 1 - kei/T + .5 kkeiei/(TT) + \frac{1}{6} k k k e i e i e i / (TTT) + \dots \quad ((7))$$

It is possible to write ((7)) as:

$$\exp(-kei/T) \text{ approx} = -kei/T + \sqrt{1.5 kkeiei/(TT) + \frac{1}{6} k k k e i e i e i / (TTT)} + \dots \quad ((8))$$

((8)) to the power $1/k$ is guaranteed to yield $\exp(-ei/T)$ in the $k=0$ limit, but does not satisfy:

$$p(ei) p(-ei) = 1 \quad ((9))$$

Furthermore, a possibility of the quadratic form is now:

$$5 p(e) - .5[1 + \frac{1}{6} k k k e i e i e i / (TTT)] / p(e) = -kei/T \quad ((10))$$

This yields a new $-\exp 3k(-ei/T)$ for $p(e)$. Dividing the LHS of ((10)) by k yields a new form for $\ln 3k(p)$ where 3 indicates that one has a cubic expansion.

The question arises, however, whether there is any physical significance to ((10)). Certainly the feature ((9)) is lost and ((10)) is not symmetrical at all, but it does contain the cubic expansion, albeit in a biased form linked with $1/p(e)$ instead of $p(e)$. Nevertheless, the $ei/T \ll 1$ approach does seem to suggest that one consider a cubic expansion if one considers a quadratic one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we provide a more direct quadratic approximation to $\exp(-kei/T)$ which automatically yields the base function of the Kaniadakis $\exp k(-ei/T)$ and shows that it is a solution of a quadratic equation. This immediately yields a form for $\ln k(ei)$ as well as $p(ei)p(-ei)=1$. We suggest that if one considers a quadratic expansion in ei/T , one should also try

a cubic one. One may still use a sqrt approximation combining $kke^{ei}/(TT)$ and $kkkeieiei/(TTT)$ in the sqrt together with 1. The resulting $\exp(3k(-ei/T))$ (3 written for the cubic solution) becomes $\exp(-ei/T)$ for $k=0$, but one no longer has $p(e)p(-ei)$. One may also still write a quadratic equation, but it is not symmetrical and it is not clear if it has any physical relevance. Nevertheless, there is no rule which dictates that one must stop a quadratic expansion and $p(e)p(-e) = 1$ does not hold in the Tsallis case and so perhaps does not need to hold for the cubic expansion either.